

Deterministic, Model-Independent Grounding-Integrity Mechanisms for Retrieval-Augmented and Agentic Language-Model Systems

A defensive publication / prior-art disclosure

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implementation: RAGchat (`cyber-assess-chat`), an offline retrieval-augmented document-review application, Apache-2.0 licensed. **License (this text):** [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\)](#). The RAGchat source code is separately licensed under Apache-2.0. **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.20951506](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20951506) (Zenodo)

0. Notice and purpose of this disclosure

This document is published to establish **prior art**. It describes, in enabling detail, a family of techniques for guaranteeing and improving the *grounding integrity* of retrieval-augmented and agentic large-language-model (LLM) systems. The techniques are deterministic and **independent of the underlying language model**.

The author's intent is defensive: to place these methods, and their obvious variants, in the public record as of the disclosure date so that they remain free for anyone to use and cannot be removed from the public domain by a later patent. The author retains copyright in this text. Authorship is asserted over the specific contributions as scoped and distinguished in §14 (Related work); the author does **not** claim priority over every constituent primitive — several have established prior art, which §14 identifies and distinguishes. This manuscript text is licensed under the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](#): anyone may copy, redistribute, and adapt it for any purpose, including patent prosecution and prior-art search, provided the author is credited (see *How to cite this disclosure*, below). The license applies to this manuscript text only; it is separate from the Apache-2.0 license of the RAGchat source code and grants no patent rights.

This is a technical disclosure, not legal advice.

Each technique below is presented as (i) the problem it solves, (ii) an enabling description with language-neutral pseudocode and, where load-bearing, verbatim matching expressions, (iii) a worked example, and (iv) an explicit, non-exhaustive enumeration of variants and equivalents — the latter included specifically to pre-empt narrow patent claims over obvious design choices.

1. Abstract

Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) and tool-using LLM agents routinely emit *citations* — references that purport to tie a generated claim to a retrieved source. A well-known failure mode is the **dangling or fabricated citation**: a citation marker that resolves to nothing, because the model invented it, mis-numbered it, or copied a stale marker from earlier context. Existing mitigations largely rely on the model to police itself (prompting, self-critique) or on post-hoc fact-checking that is itself model-based and probabilistic.

This disclosure describes a set of **deterministic, model-independent** mechanisms that together make citation integrity an *invariant of the system* rather than a behavior to be hoped for:

- **(A) A stable cross-tool evidence registry with an epistemic-provenance ranking and a citation-lifecycle guard.** Every retrieved item — regardless of which tool produced it — is assigned a stable identifier in a single append-only, de-duplicated registry. A citation is *valid* iff its identifier is a member of that registry. A three-stage lifecycle enforces this: **detect** dangling citations by integer set-membership; **bounce** a draft once, asking the model to re-ground or remove the offending citation; and, as a guarantee, **strip** any survivor at ship time — including *compound-citation surgery* that deletes only the invalid index from a multi-reference marker while preserving co-cited valid indices. An evidence legend is generated from the same registry so that every surviving marker resolves by construction. The same registry is **carried across a human-feedback revision** (§5.8), so a kept sentence keeps its resolving citation while a genuinely new claim must earn a fresh in-range identifier.
- **(B) Conversation recall as derived evidence, with citation-namespace sanitization.** Prior turns of the same conversation are recalled and fed back through the *same* evidence registry as first-class but *derived* evidence, after scrubbing each recalled turn's own citation markers and machine-generated legend so that stale, cross-run identifiers cannot resurface as new dangling citations.
- **(C) Corpus-verification of absence/negative claims before delivery.** Claims that something is "not specified / not mentioned / absent" are detected, re-checked by *fresh* retrieval against the corpus, and judged by an evidence-only model pass; claimed gaps the documents actually contain are flagged as likely-false. The mechanism is *fail-open* and *asymmetric*: it can only add a hedged advisory, never suppress a genuine gap or block an answer.
- **(D) Multi-point domain-entity canonicalization.** A single per-request entity lexicon is applied at three points — input prompt anchoring, output repair, and retrieval-query bridging — to repair model-garbled domain identifiers (e.g. QM_LB / QLMB → QMLB) and bridge acronym↔expansion, using a bounded edit-distance with a single-winner ambiguity guard.
- **(E) Full-document re-grounding for enumeration steps.** For inventory/enumeration sub-tasks, the system re-grounds on the *full indexed text* of each surfaced document (not only the top-ranked chunks) and instructs the model to enumerate every named item verbatim, preventing precise-but-low-ranking content from being dropped into a false "not specified" gap.

- **(F) Detection of referenced-but-unindexed source documents.** When the evidence cites a companion document (an appendix, a named policy, a diagram) that is not in the indexed corpus, a deterministic, high-precision scan — excluding cited external standards — flags it, optionally narrowed by a fail-open materiality judge, and appends a hedged "potential missing sources" advisory. Like (C), it is *asymmetric and fail-open*: it can only add an advisory, never block an answer or hide a real gap.

These mechanisms compose into a defense-in-depth architecture in which the correctness of citations, the truthfulness of absence claims, and the completeness of the cited source pack do not depend on the goodwill or competence of the language model.

2. Field and background

2.1 Field

Information-retrieval-augmented natural-language generation; tool-using ("agentic") LLM systems; question answering and document review over a fixed corpus; systems that present source citations to a user.

2.2 The problem

A RAG or agent system retrieves passages ("evidence") and asks an LLM to answer using them, typically requesting that the model cite evidence by some marker (a number, a bracketed id, a footnote). Because the LLM generates text token-by-token from a probability distribution, the citation markers it emits are **not guaranteed** to correspond to anything that was actually retrieved. Common pathologies:

1. **Fabricated citation** — the model emits [E7] though only three pieces of evidence exist.
2. **Mis-numbered citation** — the model cites the right idea but the wrong index.
3. **Stale citation** — the model copies a citation marker out of prior context (a previous answer, a recalled conversation turn, a few-shot example) whose numbering is meaningless in the current context.
4. **Compound contamination** — a single marker references several indices, e.g. [E1, E9], of which some are valid and some are not.
5. **False absence claim** — the model asserts the corpus does not contain something that it in fact does, because a single similarity query failed to surface the relevant passage (it ranked low, or used different vocabulary).
6. **Garbled domain identifiers** — the model corrupts a domain-specific acronym or code (spacing, casing, transposition), breaking both readability and any downstream string match.

2.3 Limitations of existing approaches

Prevailing mitigations fall into two families, both probabilistic:

- **Model-internal policing** — instructions ("only cite provided sources"), self-consistency, or self-critique. These reduce but do not eliminate the pathologies, because the same stochastic generator is asked to be its own guarantor.
- **Model-based post-hoc verification** — a second LLM pass that "fact-checks" the answer. This is itself probabilistic and can hallucinate, and typically does not specifically address citation *resolvability* or the stale/compound cases.

This disclosure treats citation resolvability as a **deterministic invariant** computed by ordinary program logic (set membership, string rewriting) outside the model — so that user-visible output cannot contain a citation that resolves to nothing, regardless of what the model does — and adds targeted corpus re-checks for the absence-claim case. Deterministic citation processing is not itself new (the production system Onyx applies a comparable membership-based primitive; see §14.2); the contribution here is the cross-tool lifecycle, provenance model, and offline model-independence around it, together with the absence-claim and entity-canonicalization mechanisms.

3. Terminology

- **Evidence item / hit** — a retrieved unit (a document chunk, a document summary, a recalled conversation turn) with associated metadata (source id, location, role).
 - **Evidence registry** — an ordered, de-duplicated, append-only collection of evidence items gathered during the processing of one user request.
 - **Evidence identifier ([E#])** — a stable label for an evidence item; in the reference implementation, the item's 1-based position in the registry.
 - **Citation / citation marker** — a token in generated text that references one or more evidence identifiers, e.g. [E3] or the compound [E1, E3] .
 - **Dangling citation** — a citation whose identifier is not a member of the current registry (resolves to nothing).
 - **Provenance / epistemic role** — whether an evidence item is *primary* (grounded in a corpus document; e.g. roles `subject` , `reference`) or *derived* (e.g. a recalled prior answer, role `history`).
 - **Absence claim** — a statement asserting that the corpus does not contain, specify, or mention some thing.
 - **Canonical entity** — the authoritative spelling of a domain identifier (acronym/code) recorded in a per-project lexicon.
-

4. System context (non-limiting)

The techniques are described in the context of a bounded agentic loop, but none of them is limited to that context (see §12–§13). The loop is the standard *orchestrator* → *tools* → *draft* → *evaluate* → *revise* shape:

```
warm-start (classify the query; build a coverage checklist if broad)
repeat up to CYCLE_BUDGET times:
  DECIDE : the orchestrator emits one structured action (call a tool, or produce a
draft answer)
  ACT    : if a tool call -> run the tool; register any returned evidence into the
registry
  DRAFT  : if a draft -> run deterministic guards (incl. the citation lifecycle, §6.3)
  EVALUATE: a critic scores faithfulness/coverage
  REVISE : if below threshold and budget remains, feed back and loop
finalize: clean -> strip dangling citations -> append evidence legend -> deliver
```

The evidence registry (A) is populated during ACT; the citation lifecycle (A) operates at DRAFT and at finalize; conversation recall (B) is one of the tools; absence-claim verification (C) and full-document re-grounding (E) appear in the analogous fixed-plan ("multi-step") pipeline; entity canonicalization (D) operates across input, output and retrieval throughout.

5. Technique A — Deterministic grounding-integrity enforcement

This is the central technique. It comprises (A.1) a stable cross-tool evidence registry, (A.2) an epistemic-provenance ranking, (A.3) a citation-lifecycle guard, and (A.4) a registry-derived evidence legend, supported by (A.5) deterministic grounding guards.

5.1 (A.1) Stable cross-tool evidence registry

Idea. Maintain, for the duration of one user request, a single ordered list of evidence items. Each item's stable identifier is its position in the list. *Every* evidence-producing tool feeds this one list through one code path; navigational or non-source tools feed nothing. Identifiers, once assigned, never change.

Data structures.

```
gathered : ordered list of evidence items      # the registry; [E#] := 1-based index
seen      : map from dedup-key -> assigned index # de-duplication
```

Registration (called after every tool invocation that returns evidence).

```
function register_evidence(hits, gathered, seen):
  indices = []
  for h in hits:
    key = h.source_chunk_id if h has a stable source id else unique_object_key(h)
    if key not in seen:
```

```

gathered.append(h)
seen[key] = length(gathered)      # 1-based position == [E#]
indices.append(seen[key])
return indices                    # per-hit identifiers, for transcript
rendering

```

Salient, deliberate properties:

- **Stable, monotonic ids.** The id is the first-seen position; a repeated item maps back to its original id. The list is append-only; ids are never renumbered mid-request.
- **De-duplication by source key**, with a per-object fallback so an item lacking a stable source id is never silently merged with another.
- **Tool-agnostic.** The registration site branches only on "did this tool return evidence?" — so a corpus search, a document-summary tool, and a conversation-recall tool (Technique B) all share one id space. A purely navigational tool (e.g. "list documents") returns no evidence and therefore consumes no id.
- **Ids assigned at gather time**, not at draft/finalize time, so the model sees stable ids in its working context as it reasons.

5.2 (A.2) Epistemic-provenance ranking (primary vs derived)

Each evidence item carries a *role*. Roles partition into **primary** (grounded in a corpus document) and **derived** (e.g. a recalled prior answer). The system enforces a **source-precedence** ordering — *reference > subject > model training knowledge*, with derived (e.g. conversation history) explicitly subordinate: it may be reused or reformatted, but any *new* factual/currency/compliance claim resting only on derived evidence must be re-grounded in a primary item. The provenance is (i) stored on the item, (ii) surfaced to the user in the legend as a role tag, and (iii) used by the evaluator's rubric to score a new claim resting solely on derived evidence as a faithfulness gap. Provenance can be a single role field; no separate flag is required.

5.3 (A.3) The citation-lifecycle guard: detect → bounce → strip

This is the mechanism that makes citation resolvability an invariant. It has three stages and a key ordering constraint.

5.3.1 Detect (by integer set-membership)

Parse citation markers from generated text and test each referenced index against the registry's id range.

Verbatim matching expression (reference implementation), tolerant of single and compound markers and of an omitted leading E on subsequent indices:

```
CITATION_MARKER := \[E\d+(?:\s*,\s*E?\d+)*\]
```

```

function cited_indices(text):
    indices = empty set
    for each match m of CITATION_MARKER in text:
        for each maximal digit-run d in m:
            indices.add(integer(d))
    return indices

function dangling_citations(text, n):          # n = size of registry
    return { i in cited_indices(text) : i < 1 or i > n }

```

A citation is dangling **iff** its index falls outside the closed integer range `[1, n]`. This is pure set membership — no model involved.

5.3.2 Bounce (bounded, one-shot correction)

On a draft containing dangling citations, return control to the orchestrator *once* with a precise, actionable message, then continue the loop:

```

if cite_bounces < BOUNCE_BUDGET (default 1):
    d = dangling_citations(draft, size(gathered))
    if d is non-empty:
        cite_bounces += 1
        remember draft as best-so-far
        append feedback message naming the exact offending markers and the legal
            range [E1..En], instructing: for each, either run a search to ground
            the claim and cite the real [E#], or drop the claim/citation
        continue          # costs one loop cycle; does not consume the revise budget

```

The feedback explicitly enumerates the offending markers and offers the two—and only two—valid remedies (re-ground, or remove). The bounce is *best-effort correction*; the guarantee is the next stage.

5.3.3 Strip (the guarantee, with compound-citation surgery)

At every finalize path, rewrite the text so that no surviving marker can dangle. Per marker:

```

function strip_dangling(text, n):
    function fix(marker):
        idxs = [ integer(d) for each digit-run d in marker ]
        valid = [ i for i in idxs if 1 <= i <= n ]
        if valid is empty:          return ""          # delete whole marker
        if length(valid) == length(idxs): return marker # untouched (all
valid)
        return "[" + join(", ", ["E"+i for i in valid]) + "]" # rebuild from valid
subset
        text = replace each CITATION_MARKER in text using fix
        text = collapse runs of 2+ spaces/tabs to one space # tidy the wake of a
deletion
        text = remove any space immediately before . , ; : )
    return text

```

The **compound-citation surgery** is the load-bearing detail: for a mixed marker such as [E1, E9] when only [E1..E3] exist, the valid index is preserved and the dangling one removed, yielding [E1]. An all-invalid marker is deleted entirely; an all-valid marker is returned byte-for-byte unchanged (a correct citation is never reformatted).

5.3.4 Ordering constraint (why it is a closed guarantee)

At finalize the operations run in a fixed order:

```
final := clean_model_output(raw)
final := strip_dangling(final, size(gathered))
final := append_evidence_legend(final, gathered) # legend lists exactly [E1..En]
```

Because the strip runs **before** the legend is appended, and the legend enumerates exactly the ids [E1..En], every citation marker remaining in the body is necessarily in range and therefore resolves to a legend entry. The guarantee holds on *every* termination path (accepted, budget-exhausted, no-progress, error fallback), because all paths funnel through the same finalize routine.

5.4 (A.4) Registry-derived evidence legend

```
function append_evidence_legend(answer, gathered):
  if gathered is empty: return answer
  lines = ["", "### Evidence", ""]
  for i, h in enumerate(gathered, start=1):
    location = h.filename or h.path or "?"
    pages    = format h.page_numbers if any
    role     = "[" + h.role + "]" if h.role else ""
    lines.append("- **[E" + i + "]** " + location + pages + " " + role)
  return rstrip(answer) + newline + join(newline, lines)
```

The legend is generated from the registry, not from the model's text, so it is always internally consistent with the ids the strip preserved.

5.5 (A.5) Supporting deterministic grounding guards

The following guards reinforce grounding without any additional model calls. Each is bounded by its own counter so an unsatisfiable condition cannot trap the loop:

- **Grounding backstop search.** If the loop reaches a forced answer having never run a corpus search, run exactly one search on the raw user query and register its hits — so a forced synthesis has real retrieved evidence to cite rather than fabricating ids. (Fail-open.)
- **Coverage bounce** (bounded, e.g. ≤ 2). If a pre-built coverage checklist has a facet whose distinctive tokens are all absent from the draft, bounce with the missing facet.
- **Reference-grounding gate** (one-shot). If the query is of a kind that must be measured against reference standards, those standards exist in the corpus, and none were retrieved, bounce.
- **Unexamined-documents bounce** (one-shot, broad queries). If a subject document contributed zero evidence to a broad review, bounce listing it.

- **Empty-draft, think-loop, and search-deduplication guards.** Reject an empty draft; forbid consecutive no-op "think" actions past a threshold; suppress a near-duplicate search (token-set Jaccard \geq a threshold, e.g. 0.8) so the budget is not wasted.

5.6 Worked example (A)

Registry after gathering: gathered = [c1, c2, c3], so valid ids are {1,2,3}.

Draft produced by the model:

"TLS 1.3 is required [E2]. Legacy renegotiation is disallowed [E1, E9]. Key escrow is mandated [E7]."

- **Detect:** cited_indices = {2,1,9,7}; dangling = {9,7}.
- **Bounce (once):** "Your draft cites [E7], [E9], which do not resolve — only [E1]..[E3] exist. For each, run a search to ground it and cite the real [E#], or drop the claim/citation. Then redraft."
- Suppose the model redrafts but still writes [E1, E9] and drops the [E7] sentence.
- **Strip at finalize:** [E1, E9] → [E1] (compound surgery); no other danglers.
- **Legend appended:** lists [E1]..[E3]. Final text contains only [E1], [E2], which resolve. Invariant holds.

5.7 Variants and equivalents (A) — non-exhaustive

To pre-empt narrow claims, the following design choices are explicitly disclosed as within the scope of this technique:

1. **Identifier scheme.** The id may be a 1-based or 0-based index, a per-request counter, a UUID, a content hash, or any stable token; "membership" is tested against whatever id space the registry uses.
2. **Marker syntax.** The citation may be [E#], [#], [n], a superscript footnote, {{cite:id}}, an inline hyperlink/anchor, or any parseable reference; the detect/strip stages adapt the matching expression accordingly.
3. **De-duplication key.** Source-chunk id, document id + offset, content hash, or normalized text; with or without a per-object fallback.
4. **Bounce budget.** Zero (strip only), one, or N; with or without escalating feedback; with or without consuming a separate revise budget.
5. **Strip policy for compounds.** Preserve the valid subset (as disclosed), or delete the whole compound, or annotate the removed index — the disclosed and preferred form preserves co-cited valid indices.
6. **Placement.** Detect/strip at finalize only; at each draft; streaming (rewriting tokens as emitted); or at an API/middleware boundary independent of the agent.

7. **Cross-tool scope.** One registry shared across any number and kind of evidence-producing tools, including web search, SQL/database tools, code-execution outputs, and conversation recall (Technique B).
8. **Legend form.** Inline legend, sidebar, structured JSON, hyperlinks, or hover cards — all derived from the same registry after the strip.
9. **Model independence.** Applicable to any autoregressive or non-autoregressive generator, any vendor, local or remote, with or without tool-calling support.

5.8 Carrying the registry across a human-feedback revision

A revision is where citation integrity is easiest to lose: a user reviews an answer, asks for changes, and a naive re-run starts with an empty registry — so the prior answer's [E#] either break or the model re-fabricates support for sentences it is keeping. The same registry (§5.1) is therefore *carried forward* into a feedback-steered re-run, so the invariant of §5.3 holds across revisions.

Mechanism: the parent run's gathered evidence is reconstructed (de-duplicated by source id, reproducing the same [E1..En]) and each ordinary chunk is re-fetched at full fidelity by its id; these *carried hits* are registered **first**, so they occupy the same stable identifiers, a synthetic tool message presents them as already-gathered, and the grounding backstop is marked satisfied (no redundant re-search). The revision directive then states that the prior [E#] are carried and resolve — *keep them on any sentence you keep, run new searches only for the points the feedback raises, and cite a fresh [E#] only for a genuinely new claim* — with the user's feedback authoritative (it outranks the evaluator) and the original task re-anchoring scope (the revision refines or extends; it does not narrow). If evidence cannot be carried (a fallback), the prior answer's [E#] are stripped instead and every kept claim must be re-grounded.

```
on a feedback-steered revision of a prior run:
  carried = reconstruct_parent_evidence(parent) # dedup by id -> [E1..En]
  register_evidence(carried, gathered, seen)   # same stable ids, registered first
  searched = true                             # suppress the grounding backstop
  directive: "the prior [E#] are carried and resolve; keep them on kept
             sentences; search only for what the feedback raises; a new
             claim earns a fresh [E#]"
  run the normal loop; finalize still applies detect -> bounce -> strip (§5.3)
```

Because the carried evidence occupies the same identifiers and the finalize-time strip (§5.3.3) still runs, a kept sentence's citation resolves by construction and any unsupported new citation is removed — so human-in-the-loop revision cannot degrade grounding integrity.

6. Technique B — Conversation recall as derived evidence, with citation-namespace sanitization

6.1 Problem

When an agent can recall earlier turns of the *same* conversation (to honor "as you said before", "reformat the prior assessment"), naive reuse re-injects the recalled text verbatim — including that earlier turn's own citation markers and its machine-generated evidence legend. Those ids belong to a *different* request's registry; if reused, the model parrots them as new citations that dangle in the current request.

6.2 Idea

Recall prior turns and feed them into the *same* evidence registry (Technique A.1) as first-class but **derived** evidence (role `history`), with **no parallel evidence machinery** — a recalled turn gets a stable `[E#]` exactly like a document chunk. Before reuse, **sanitize the citation namespace**: strip the recalled turn's own inline markers and its machine legend so cross-request ids cannot resurface.

6.3 Enabling description

Selection. A recall tool accepts a scope and optional query:

```
scope = "latest"           -> return the most recent prior assistant turn (one item)
scope = "all", no query    -> return the most recent k turns (recency order)
scope = "all", with query  -> return the top-k prior turns by simple token-overlap
                           (query tokens of length >= 2 counted as substrings),
                           ties broken by recency
```

Exclusion of the in-flight turn. The current user turn is persisted *before* the tool is constructed; the tool is given that turn's id and filters it out, so the agent can never "recall" the question it is currently answering.

Sanitization (the core). Each recalled turn's text is cleaned before becoming an evidence item, removing the machine legend *first* (so its bulleted ids are gone before inline-marker removal), then inline markers, then tidying whitespace:

```
function sanitize_recalled(text):
  text = remove EVIDENCE_LEGEND_BLOCK from text
  text = remove every CITATION_MARKER from text
  text = collapse runs of 2+ spaces to one
  return trim(text)
```

Verbatim matching expressions (reference implementation):

```
CITATION_MARKER      := [ \t]?\[E\d+(?:[ \t]*,[ \t]*E?\d+)*\]
EVIDENCE_LEGEND_BLOCK := \n#{1,6}[ \t]+Evidence[ \t]*\n+
```

```
(?:[ \t]*[-*][ \t]+\*\*[E\d+]\*\*.*(?:\n|$))+
\s*\Z      # (case-insensitive)
```

The legend expression is deliberately pinned to the *exact shape the legend generator emits* — a heading whose text is "Evidence" immediately followed by one or more `**[E#]**` ... bullets, anchored to end-of-text — so that a *prose* "Evidence" section (e.g. a verdict/evidence/gaps narrative) is **not** destroyed. This precision is essential: the sanitizer must remove machine bookkeeping without harming substantive content.

Construction as derived evidence. Each sanitized turn becomes an ordinary evidence item with role `history`, a stable source key (`history:<message-id>`), a human-readable location ("conversation turn N (role)"), and a content cap (e.g. 2000 chars). It then flows through the *unmodified* `register_evidence` path (A.1), receiving a stable `[E#]` and a `[history]` tag in the legend.

On-by-default; fail-soft. The tool is enabled whenever a chat-history store is wired (no separate flag). If, after excluding the in-flight turn, nothing usable remains, the tool returns an evidence-free informational message — consuming no id.

Precedence. Per A.2, recalled `history` evidence is derived: reuse/reformat is allowed, but a *new* fact resting only on it is scored as a faithfulness gap, driving re-grounding in a primary `[E#]`.

6.4 Worked example (B)

A prior answer being recalled contains: "...use AES-256 `[E2]` .\n\n### Evidence\n- `[E2]` crypto.pdf p.4 [subject]". In the *current* request only `[E1]` has been gathered so far. Without sanitization the model might echo "`[E2]`", which dangles. After `sanitize_recalled`, the recalled content is "...use AES-256." with no markers and no legend; it is registered as, say, `[E2]` `conversation turn 3 (assistant)` `[history]`. Any citation the model now makes to it resolves; no stale id leaks.

6.5 Variants and equivalents (B) — non-exhaustive

1. **Selection policy.** Latest-only; last-k; lexical overlap; embedding similarity; recency-weighted; per-role (user/assistant) filtering.
2. **Granularity.** Whole turns, message spans, or summaries of turns.
3. **Sanitization target.** Any citation/footnote syntax and any machine-legend/appendix format; removal by regex, by structured-markup parsing, or by stripping a known delimiter region.
4. **Provenance handling.** A distinct derived role, a numeric trust weight, or a separate namespace that is later merged.
5. **Source of recalled material.** The same conversation, a different prior session, or any text that carries foreign citation namespaces (few-shot exemplars, pasted prior reports) — the sanitization applies equally.
6. **Reuse of the primary registry** vs. a parallel one reconciled at finalize — the disclosed and preferred form reuses the primary registry verbatim.

7. Technique C – Corpus-verification of absence/negative claims before delivery

7.1 Problem

A grounded answer may assert a *gap* ("the standard does not specify cipher suites") that is actually false – the content exists but a single retrieval query missed it (low rank, vocabulary mismatch). Shipping a false gap is a serious correctness failure in review/compliance settings.

7.2 Idea

After composing the answer but before delivery, **detect absence claims, re-retrieve** fresh evidence for each using the claim text itself as the query, and have an **evidence-only** model pass judge whether the supposedly-absent content is in fact present; **flag** (do not silently fix) likely-false gaps as a hedged advisory. The mechanism is **fail-open** and **asymmetric** – it can only *add* a warning, never remove a genuine gap or block the answer.

7.3 Enabling description

Detect. Scan the answer line-by-line; strip leading list/heading/emphasis markup; reject lines shorter than a small minimum (e.g. 12 chars); match an absence pattern; de-duplicate case-insensitively; return the cleaned lines (the whole line is used later as the retrieval query – no separate subject extraction).

Verbatim absence pattern (reference implementation), case-insensitive, word-bounded:

```
ABSENCE :=
  \b(?:
    not
    (?:(specified|listed|defined|addressed|mentioned|documented|included|provided|stated)
      | does not (?:(specify|list|define|address|mention|include|provide|state|name)
      | do not (?:(specify|list|define|address|mention|include|provide|state|name)
      | no specific | not explicitly
      | fails? to (?:(specify|list|define|address|mention|name)
      | lacks? (?:(a |an |any )?(?:specific|explicit|defined)
      | absence of | silent on
    )\b
```

Re-retrieve and judge.

```
function verify_absence_claims(answer, retriever, llm, K=6, MAX_CLAIMS=6):
  claims = detect_absence_claims(answer)[:MAX_CLAIMS]
  if claims is empty: return [] # no model call
  per_claim_hits = []
  for claim in claims:
    hits = try retriever.retrieve(claim, k=K, role=SUBJECT) # fresh, corpus-scoped
            on TypeError: retriever.retrieve(claim, k=K) # signature fallback
```

```

        on any error: [] # per-claim fail-soft
    per_claim_hits.append(hits)
    if no claim produced any hits: return [] # no model call
    prompt = batched_listing: "CLAIM i: <claim>\nEVIDENCE:\n - <hit text [:400]> ..." #
up to 4 hits/claim
    raw = try llm.generate(prompt, temperature=0, max_tokens=128) # one batched call
        on any error: return [] # fail-open
    contradicted = parse_first_json_int_array(raw) # claim numbers present
in evidence
    return [ claim_i with top-hit source for i in contradicted if 1 <= i <= len(claims) ]

```

The judge's instruction is explicit: decide *only from the evidence* (never the model's own knowledge) whether each supposedly-absent item is actually present, and reply with a JSON array of the contradicted claim numbers. The output parser robustly extracts the first bracketed integer array and excludes booleans.

Flag (asymmetric). Contradicted claims are rendered as an appendable advisory; an empty result yields the empty string (nothing appended):

```

△ Verification – claimed gaps contradicted by the documents
A re-check against the subject documents found content for the following
claimed gaps, so treat them as likely false gaps:
- <claim text> – see <filename> p.<pages>

```

Fail-open everywhere. No claims, no evidence, retrieval error, model error, unparseable output, or out-of-range index each results in "no advisory" — the user's answer is delivered unchanged. The mechanism can only *add* a hedged flag; it never deletes a gap the documents do not actually fill, and never blocks delivery.

7.4 Variants and equivalents (C) — non-exhaustive

1. **Detection.** Regex patterns (as disclosed), a classifier, or structured-field inspection of a typed answer.
 2. **Query formation.** Whole-claim-as-query (as disclosed), extracted subject/topic, or expanded query.
 3. **Judging.** One batched evidence-only model pass (as disclosed), per-claim passes, an entailment/NLI model, or a non-model lexical check.
 4. **Action.** Flag-only (as disclosed, asymmetric), or fix-and-rewrite, or bounce-and-revise in an interactive loop (the loop analogue), or block (not preferred — violates fail-open).
 5. **Scope.** Verify against the subject corpus, the reference corpus, or both.
 6. **Determinism knobs.** Temperature 0, capped tokens, bounded claim count, bounded hits.
-

8. Technique D – Multi-point domain-entity canonicalization

8.1 Problem

LLMs corrupt domain identifiers (acronyms, control ids, codes): inserting separators or spaces, changing case, or transposing characters (QMLB → QM_LB , QM L B , QLMB). This breaks readability, citations, and any downstream exact-match (retrieval, lookup). A purely output-side fix is fragile; a purely input-side fix (prompting) is incomplete.

8.2 Idea

Maintain a small per-project lexicon of canonical entities (and optional expansions/aliases) and apply it at **three points** that all read the **same per-request lexicon**: (1) **input** — anchor the prompt with the canonical spellings; (2) **output** — repair garbled mentions; (3) **retrieval** — canonicalize the query and bridge acronym↔expansion so either phrasing retrieves the other. A bounded edit-distance with a single-winner guard performs the fuzzy repair without mis-correcting.

8.3 Enabling description

Lexicon and seeding. Each entity has a `canonical` spelling, optional `expansion`, optional `aliases`, a `source`, and a `fuzzy` flag. Entities are seeded automatically at index time from filenames: split each filename stem on separators, keep *identifier-shaped* tokens (length ≥ 3, all-uppercase, alphanumeric) that appear in ≥ 2 filenames (so corpus-wide acronyms seed; one-offs do not). User- and discovery-sourced entities are preserved across re-seeds.

Output repair (idempotent; protects code spans first):

```
function canonicalize_text(text, lexicon):
    if lexicon empty: return text
    hide fenced/inline code spans behind sentinels
    # Stage 1a: exact whole-word, case-insensitive → canonical (for canonical + each
alias)
    # Stage 1b: separator-tolerant whole-word (separator run bounded to 0..3 chars) →
canonical
    #           (identifier-shaped targets only)
    # Stage 2: bounded edit-distance over identifier-shaped tokens:
    for each identifier-shaped token tok in text:
        best, winners = infinity, {}
        for each fuzzy entity e:
            d = damerau_levenshtein_OSA(tok, e.canonical)
            if d < best: best, winners = d, {e.canonical}
            elif d == best: winners.add(e.canonical)
        if best <= MAX_DISTANCE (=1) and |winners| == 1:
            replace tok with the single winner      # ambiguity guard: ties are left
untouched
    restore hidden code spans
    return text
```

The distance is the Optimal String Alignment (Damerau-Levenshtein restricted to adjacent transpositions), which makes a neighbor swap such as QMLB ↔ QLMB cost exactly 1 (within threshold). The **single-winner ambiguity guard** ensures that if two near-twin acronyms tie, the token is left alone rather than mis-corrected — precision over recall.

Input anchoring. Render the lexicon as a system-prompt block, e.g.:

```
DOMAIN TERMS – write each EXACTLY as shown; do not insert spaces or underscores,
change the casing, or reorder letters:
  QMLB = Quantum Machine Learning Bank
  NIST
  ...
```

injected into the resolved prompt for every chat template, biasing generation toward canonical spellings (reducing how often the output repair must fire).

Retrieval bridging. For each entity with an expansion, if the query contains one surface form but not the other, append the other as an alternate ("`<query> (alt1 | alt2)`"), bidirectionally (acronym→expansion and expansion→acronym). The query is also passed through `canonicalize_text` so a garbled query term matches. (In the reference implementation the bridged/expanded query feeds the dense arm; the keyword arm uses the original to avoid lexical noise.)

One per-request lexicon shared by all three points. A process-wide context variable holds the active lexicon for the dynamic extent of the request (set by a decorator that loads the project lexicon once). The output choke point reads it (or an explicit argument); the prompt resolver reads it for anchoring; the retriever is constructed with it. This guarantees all three points act on the *same* lexicon without threading it through every signature, and resets cleanly per request (no leakage across requests on a reused worker).

8.4 Variants and equivalents (D) – non-exhaustive

1. **Distance metric/threshold.** OSA/Damerau-Levenshtein (as disclosed), Levenshtein, Jaro-Winkler; threshold 1 or 2; with/without the identifier-shaped gate.
 2. **Ambiguity policy.** Single-winner-only (as disclosed), nearest with tie-break, or confidence-weighted.
 3. **Seeding.** From filenames (as disclosed), from headings, from an ontology, manually, or LLM-discovered; any minimum-frequency threshold.
 4. **Application points.** Any subset of {input anchoring, output repair, retrieval bridging}; the disclosed novelty is doing all three from one shared per-request lexicon.
 5. **Propagation.** Context variable (as disclosed), dependency injection, or explicit argument.
 6. **Bridging direction.** Acronym→expansion, expansion→acronym, or both; applied to dense, sparse, or both retrieval arms.
-

9. Technique E — Full-document re-grounding for enumeration steps

9.1 Problem

For an *inventory/enumeration* sub-task ("list every cipher suite", "enumerate all controls"), a single similarity query returns only top-k chunks. A precise but low-ranking passage (e.g. a cipher-suite table that does not lexically match "algorithms") is buried and omitted, producing a false "not specified" gap.

9.2 Idea

When a step is a **subject** *inventory* step (and only then), replace its top-k chunk hits with the **full indexed text** of each *surfaced* document, and instruct the model to enumerate every named item **verbatim**. Comparison/reference steps keep precise top-k chunks. The full text is reassembled from the already-indexed chunks (no re-extraction). Fail-open: a document whose full text cannot be fetched keeps its original chunks.

9.3 Enabling description

```
# Gate (all must hold):
if step.kind == "retrieve_and_answer"
  and step.role != REFERENCE           # subject (or unset) corpus only
  and hits is non-empty
  and retriever provides document_full_text:
    hits = full_document_hits(hits, retriever.document_full_text)

function full_document_hits(hits, fetch_full_text):
  group hits by document id, preserving first-appearance order
  out = []
  for each document id in order:
    text = try fetch_full_text(id) else ""      # fail-open
    if text is blank:
      out.extend(this document's original chunks)  # fallback: keep top-k
    else:
      out.append( synthetic hit {
        content = text,                          # full document text
        score   = max score among this doc's chunks,
        pages   = sorted union of the chunks' pages,
        location/role from the best chunk } )
  return out
```

`document_full_text` reassembles the document from its stored index chunks (ordered by page then row), reusing text extracted at index time rather than re-running a (slow, crash-prone) extractor.

Enumerate-verbatim prompt (the other half of the mechanism):

```
Be EXHAUSTIVE when the sub-question asks you to identify, list, or inventory
items: enumerate EVERY distinct named item in the evidence VERBATIM – each
algorithm, full cipher-suite name, protocol version, key size, curve, control
ID, and identifier – and do NOT collapse them into broad categories or omit any.
```

Naming a category (e.g. "TLS protocols") in place of the specific items (e.g. each named cipher suite) causes a false "not specified" gap downstream.

Together: the full text is brought fully into context (so nothing is buried), and the model is forced to extract item-by-item (so nothing is summarized away). This is complementary to Technique C, which is the downstream backstop that re-checks any surviving "not specified" gap.

9.4 Variants and equivalents (E) — non-exhaustive

1. **Trigger.** Step-kind/role gate (as disclosed), a query classifier ("enumerate/list/inventory" intent), or an explicit flag.
2. **Full-text source.** Reassembled from index chunks (as disclosed), a stored full-text blob, or on-demand re-extraction.
3. **Granularity.** Whole document, or section/page windows above a size threshold.
4. **Fail-open behavior.** Keep top-k on failure (as disclosed) — only ever adding completeness.
5. **Prompt form.** Verbatim-enumeration instruction with the named failure mode (as disclosed), or a structured "list" output schema.

10. Technique F — Detection of referenced-but-unindexed source documents

10.1 Problem

A review corpus often arrives **incomplete**: the indexed evidence *references* a companion document — an appendix, a named policy, an architecture diagram — that is not itself in the corpus. Answering silently "around" the gap is a correctness failure in review/compliance settings. This is distinct from Technique C: C re-checks a claimed *absence of content*; F detects a *document the evidence cites but the corpus lacks*.

10.2 Idea

Deterministically detect high-signal document references in the evidence, resolve each against the indexed inventory (separator-insensitively), and flag those that neither resolve nor are external published standards (which are *cited*, not missing). Optionally pass the survivors through a **fail-open** model "materiality" judge, attribute each to where it is cited ([E#] / file / page), and append a hedged advisory. The mechanism is conservative (precision over recall) and, like Technique C, **asymmetric and fail-open** — it can only *add* a "potential missing sources" advisory, never block an answer or hide a real gap.

10.3 Enabling description

Detect (deterministic). Extract references with two high-precision patterns: (i) explicit document filenames (`Name.pdf|docx|xlsx|pptx|csv|md`); and (ii) Title-Cased phrases ending in a document-type word (Policy | Standard | Procedure | Guideline | Framework | Specification | Diagram | Architecture | Plan | Matrix | Register | Runbook | Playbook | Agreement | Addendum | Report | Assessment | Model | Charter | Baseline | Schedule). Drop any reference containing an **external-standard marker** (nist, iso, iec, rfc, fips, pci, swift, owasp, cis, soc 2, gdpr, hipaa, sox, mitre, att&ck, ...) — those are citations, not missing pack documents. Normalize the remainder with a separator-insensitive key and drop any that **resolve** to an indexed document (two-way containment against the indexed filenames). De-duplicate, enforce a minimum length, and cap the count. (A bare "Appendix C / Annex B" pattern is deliberately *excluded* — an appendix is a section of some document, often an indexed or external one, and cannot be attributed to a distinct missing file; filenames + named documents are the high-precision signals.)

```
function find_missing_references(text, indexed_filenames):
    indexed = [ normalize(stem(f)) for f in indexed_filenames ]
    out, seen = [], {}
    for ref in filename_matches(text) + named_document_matches(text):
        if has_external_marker(ref): continue # cited standard, not missing
        key = normalize(strip_leading_article(stem(ref)))
        if len(key) < MIN or key in seen: continue
        if any(key in i or i in key for i in indexed): continue # resolves -> present
        seen.add(key); out.append(ref)
    return out[:MAX] # conservative, deduped, capped
```

Filter (optional, fail-open). Show the indexed pack and each candidate (with a short surrounding-context snippet, so the judge can spot an (OWASP) -style cited framework the candidate string alone does not reveal) to an evidence-only model pass (temperature 0, JSON `{"missing": [...]}`). Keep only candidates judged *material missing documents*. **Fail-open:** any error or unparseable reply returns the deterministic list unchanged — a flaky model can never *hide* a real gap — and the pass is a pure filter that never invents a reference.

Attribute + render. For each surviving name, locate where it is cited and render `file p.N [E#]` (de-duplicated, capped); emit a "△ Potential missing sources" advisory, or the empty string when there is nothing to flag. The advisory is appended to agent-mode and multi-step answers.

10.4 Variants and equivalents (F) — non-exhaustive

1. **Detection.** Regex patterns (as disclosed), NER, or structured-field inspection of a typed answer.
2. **Resolution.** Separator-insensitive containment (as disclosed), exact match, or bounded edit-distance (Technique D's matcher).
3. **External-standard exclusion.** Any marker list or classifier that separates a *cited standard* from an *expected companion document*.
4. **Materiality.** A fail-open model filter (as disclosed), deterministic rules, or none.

5. **Action.** Advisory-only and asymmetric (as disclosed) — never blocking, never hiding a gap.

11. Combined system: defense-in-depth

The techniques are independent but compose into layered protection:

- **Against ungrounded/dangling citations:** input anchoring (D) and the source-precedence prompt reduce errors at the source; the grounding-backstop and coverage/reference guards (A.5) ensure real evidence exists; the citation-lifecycle guard (A.3) detects, bounces, and—as a hard guarantee—strips; provenance (A.2) and recall sanitization (B) prevent derived/stale ids from contaminating the namespace; the legend (A.4) is generated from the registry so it is always consistent.
- **Against false absence claims:** full-document re-grounding with verbatim enumeration (E) prevents the gap from being created; absence-claim verification (C) is the fail-open backstop that catches any survivor before delivery.
- **Against garbled identifiers:** multi-point canonicalization (D) repairs them on input, output, and in retrieval, so citations and lookups remain exact.

Crucially, the *guarantees* (A.3 strip; C's asymmetry and fail-open) are deterministic and do not depend on the language model behaving well.

12. Generality and applicability

None of the techniques is limited to the reference implementation or its domain (document review / compliance). They apply to:

- any retrieval backend (dense, sparse, hybrid, graph, web, database, file-system);
- any generator (any vendor; local or hosted; any size; with or without native tool-calling);
- any orchestration shape (single-shot RAG, fixed multi-step plans, open-ended agent loops, multi-agent systems);
- any citation/markup convention; and
- streaming or batch generation, and middleware/proxy deployments that post-process model output independently of the application.

In particular, the citation-lifecycle guard (A.3) can be implemented as a standalone output-integrity filter at an API boundary, taking only (a) the set of valid evidence ids and (b) the generated text, and returning text in which every citation provably resolves.

13. Consolidated enumeration of disclosed variants (anti-claim)

For the avoidance of doubt, the following are expressly disclosed as part of this publication and intended to constitute prior art against later claims, whether used singly or in any combination: identifier schemes (index/counter/UUID/hash); any citation/footnote/anchor syntax; de-duplication by source id, offset, or content hash, with or without per-object fallback; assigning ids at gather time across one or many heterogeneous evidence-producing tools; an epistemic role distinguishing primary from derived evidence with a precedence rule; detecting unresolved citations by set membership over an id range; a bounded (zero/one/N) corrective bounce with id-specific feedback; a ship-time strip that deletes wholly-invalid markers and rewrites mixed markers to their valid subset, run before a registry-derived legend on every termination path; recall of prior conversation (or other foreign-namespace text) as derived evidence through the same registry after removing its inline citation markers and machine legend via shape-pinned matching; detection of absence/negative claims and their fail-open, asymmetric, evidence-only corpus re-verification with flag-only output; a single per-request entity lexicon applied to input anchoring, output repair (bounded edit-distance with single-winner ambiguity guard over identifier-shaped tokens), and bidirectional retrieval bridging; full-document re-grounding (full text reassembled from index chunks, fail-open) gated to subject inventory steps and paired with a verbatim-enumeration instruction; carrying that evidence registry across a human-feedback revision so kept citations resolve and only genuinely new claims need fresh grounding; and deterministic detection of referenced-but-unindexed source documents (high-precision filename / named-document patterns, external-standard exclusion, separator-insensitive resolution, an optional fail-open materiality filter, and a flag-only advisory).

14. Related work

RAGchat is a local, offline retrieval-augmented document-review application. Its disclosed contributions are a set of *deterministic, model-independent* enforcement mechanisms layered on an otherwise conventional substrate (a bounded agent loop; hybrid vector + BM25 retrieval with Reciprocal Rank Fusion and cross-encoder reranking; grammar-constrained JSON actions; offline local GGUF models). We organize prior work along the axes those mechanisms touch and, in each case, locate RAGchat's contribution relative to the closest art. Several constituent primitives have established prior art, which we identify and distinguish below; the contribution is the *composition*, not the primitives.

14.1 Retrieval-augmented generation and hybrid retrieval

Retrieval-augmented generation grounds a generator in retrieved passages rather than parametric memory (Lewis et al. 2020); subsequent practice and the survey of Y. Gao et al. (2023) consolidate the now-standard pipeline of dense retrieval (Karpukhin et al. 2020), embedding models such as Sentence-BERT (Reimers and Gurevych 2019), sparse lexical scoring via BM25 (Robertson and Zaragoza 2009), fusion of ranked lists by Reciprocal Rank Fusion (Cormack et al. 2009), and BERT-

based passage reranking (Nogueira and Cho 2019). RAGchat's retrieval layer is a direct composition of these conventional components and we make no claim of novelty for it. The closest system-level prior art is Astrino (2025), which likewise targets local, offline, hybrid (semantic + keyword) document QA on consumer hardware; we therefore do not position local-offline-hybrid deployment itself as a contribution. RAGchat's delta is orthogonal to retrieval quality: it concerns what happens to citations, recalled context, negative claims, and entity mentions *after* retrieval, enforced deterministically rather than left to the model.

14.2 Citations and attribution in LLMs

Most work on grounded, citable generation is *model-based*: it trains or prompts the model to emit better-supported citations, and/or evaluates support post hoc. ALCE (T. Gao et al. 2023) defines automatic citation precision/recall and shows models cite imperfectly; attributed QA is formalized and modeled by Bohnet et al. (2022); prompting strategies such as "according to ..." steer models toward quoting source text (Weller et al. 2023); and large-scale audits of generative search engines find frequent unsupported or partially-supported citations (Liu et al. 2023). Surveys of attribution (D. Li et al. 2023) catalogue these probabilistic approaches. A second line *verifies or repairs* attribution with additional model passes: RARR researches and revises model output against retrieved evidence (L. Gao et al. 2023); CEG adds a retrieval-and-verification stage to chatbot answers (W. Li et al. 2024); Think&Cite uses guided tree search with a reward model (J. Li and Ng 2024); and VeriCite adds rigorous citation verification (Qian et al. 2025). Critically, Wallat et al. (2024) show that a *well-formed* citation is frequently *unfaithful* — referential correctness and semantic support are distinct.

RAGchat's grounding-integrity mechanism is deliberately on the *referential*, not semantic, axis, and is *deterministic and model-independent*. We do **not** claim it removes unsupported or unfaithful citations — that goal is owned by the model-based attribution and verification work above, and Wallat et al. (2024) is precisely why we scope the claim narrowly. RAGchat instead enforces that every emitted citation *resolves to a real gathered evidence item*: one append-only, de-duplicated evidence registry assigns each item a stable 1-based id, a citation is valid iff its id lies in $[1, N]$, dangling citations are detected by integer set-membership, the draft is bounced once to re-ground or remove, and any survivor is stripped at finalize — including compound-citation surgery that drops the invalid index from `[E1, E9]` while keeping the valid one — before a registry-derived legend is appended.

We must **concede the core deterministic primitive to existing production art**. The open-source Onyx system's citation processor (`backend/onyx/chat/citation_processor.py`, <https://github.com/onyx-dot-app/onyx>) already performs, model-free, an ordered first-citation registry, membership-based dropping of citation numbers that map to no retrieved document, and per-index handling of compound citations that retains only the valid indices; we verified this against its source. RAGchat's defensible delta is therefore *not* the primitive but its lifecycle and scope: (i) a single registry unified across *heterogeneous tools* — corpus search, document summarization, and conversation recall — rather than over a single answer's token stream; (ii) a *one-shot bounce that asks the model to re-ground or remove before* the deterministic strip is applied, rather than a silent drop only; (iii) an explicit *provenance distinction* between primary (document) and derived (e.g.

conversation) evidence with a precedence rule; and (iv) operation with *no provider dependency*, entirely offline on local models. Relative to the Anthropic Citations API (<https://platform.claude.com/docs/en/docs/build-with-claude/citations>) — the closest deterministic-axis precedent, a hosted feature whose returned citations are guaranteed to be valid pointers into the supplied documents — RAGchat differs in the cross-tool unification, the post-hoc bounce-then-strip lifecycle, the provenance precedence, and provider independence. Recent work on citation-hallucination detection (FACTUM, Dassen et al. 2026; Ovcharov 2026) pursues the same referential-integrity goal with mechanistic or citation-graph methods and is concurrent or later art relative to this disclosure.

14.3 Hallucination, factuality, abstention, and verifying negative claims

Hallucination in generation is surveyed broadly (Ji et al. 2023; Huang et al. 2023). Factual-precision and detection methods are predominantly model-based: FactScore decomposes long-form text into atomic facts for scoring (Min et al. 2023); SelfCheckGPT samples the model for self-consistency (Manakul et al. 2023); FEVER frames claim verification against evidence (Thorne et al. 2018). A complementary line studies *abstention and false presuppositions*: whether models know what they do not know (Yin et al. 2023), answering unanswerable questions (Rajpurkar et al. 2018), open-domain questions with false presuppositions (Yu et al. 2023), and mitigating false-premise hallucinations (Yuan et al. 2024). RGB benchmarks RAG robustness including negative rejection (Chen et al. 2024).

RAGchat's absence-verification mechanism addresses an adjacent but distinct failure: a *self-asserted* gap. After generation it detects the system's own "not specified / not mentioned" claims, re-retrieves fresh evidence per claim, and runs an evidence-only LLM judge that flags claimed gaps the corpus actually contains. The contribution is best framed as a *deterministic trigger plus bounded LLM adjudication*, and it differs from the prior art in two ways those lines do not jointly cover: prior work targets *input* presuppositions or rejection decisions (the CREPE / RGB / FEVER family) or *edits the model's positive claims* (RARR and chain-of-verification-style revision), whereas RAGchat re-verifies its *own negative claims*. It is also *asymmetric and fail-open*: it can only append a hedged advisory and can never block, hide, or convert a genuine gap — a real corpus absence is preserved. We claim the composition and the asymmetric, advisory-only policy, not a new verification model. The same conditional design motivates RAGchat's full-document re-grounding for enumeration steps: when (and only when) a step must enumerate items, it is fed each surfaced document's full indexed text rather than top-k chunks (mitigating the long-context "buried evidence" effect that RGB and related benchmarks probe), so precise low-ranking content is not dropped into a false "not specified" gap.

14.4 Entity normalization, approximate string matching, and conversation memory

RAGchat canonicalizes domain entities (e.g. garbled acronyms) from a single per-request lexicon applied at three sites: input (prompt anchoring), output (repair), and retrieval (acronym/expansion bridging). The output repair uses bounded edit distance — Damerau–Levenshtein / optimal string alignment with distance ≤ 1 — over identifier-shaped tokens, with a single-winner guard that refuses ambiguous corrections. Every constituent is textbook: Levenshtein (1966) and Damerau (1964) edit

distance; entity linking and normalization against a reference set (Shen et al. 2015; Sevgili et al. 2022); acronym identification and disambiguation (Veyseh et al. 2020); record-linkage blocking and matching (Christen 2012); and even the input-side anchoring intuition has precedent in prompting models to quote canonical source spans (Weller et al. 2023). We therefore claim a *composition*, not an algorithm: one lexicon driving all three sites plus the single-winner ambiguity guard. We note the limitation that the distance- ≤ 1 OSA rule does not cover combined lowercasing-plus-transposition errors.

For conversation recall, long-term LLM memory has been studied extensively (MemGPT, Packer et al. 2023; MemoryBank, Zhong et al. 2024; generative agents, Park et al. 2023; long-term conversational-memory evaluation, Maharana et al. 2024). RAGchat does not contribute a new memory architecture; it reuses retrieval over prior turns. Its narrow addition is a *consequence-guard of the citation mechanism* (§14.2): prior turns enter as *derived* evidence through the same registry, and a citation-namespace sanitization step strips a recalled turn's own [E#] markers and machine legend so stale cross-run ids cannot resurface as dangling citations. We present this as the cleanest item with no prior art we could identify, while acknowledging that its scope is narrow and contingent on the registry of §14.2.

14.5 Agentic LLM patterns and constrained decoding

RAGchat's control loop is a bounded decide–act–draft–evaluate–revise cycle, an instance of the now-standard reasoning-and-acting pattern (ReAct, Yao et al. 2023) with a self-reflective critique step in the spirit of Self-RAG (Asai et al. 2024). Actions are emitted as grammar-constrained (GBNF) JSON. We treat the agent loop, the evaluator step, and constrained decoding as conventional engineering substrate and make no novelty claim for them; their role here is to provide the deterministic seams at which the enforcement mechanisms above attach.

14.6 Summary of RAGchat's delta

Against this landscape, RAGchat's contribution is not a new model, retriever, or attribution algorithm, but a coherent set of *deterministic, model-independent, offline* enforcement mechanisms over a conventional RAG-agent substrate. Conceding the citation primitive to Onyx and the local-offline-hybrid framing to Astrino (2025), the defensible delta is: a single evidence registry unified across heterogeneous tools (search, summary, and conversation-recall-as-derived-evidence) with a bounce-before-strip lifecycle and provenance precedence; citation-namespace sanitization as a consequence-guard on recalled context; asymmetric, fail-open re-verification of the system's *own* negative claims via deterministic trigger plus bounded adjudication; a one-lexicon / three-site entity-canonicalization composition with a single-winner guard; and a conditional full-document re-grounding tie for enumeration steps that reinforces the absence-verification mechanism. Each is modest individually; together they form a determinism-first integrity layer that operates without any reliance on a hosted model or network.

15. Reference implementation

A complete reference implementation exists (RAGchat / `cyber-assess-chat`). Its source is **licensed** under the Apache License 2.0; it may be published separately, but the techniques above are fully specified by their descriptions and pseudocode and do not depend on access to that source. The relevant modules (for an implementer):

- Grounding-integrity (A): the agent runner's evidence registry, citation detection/bounce/strip, and legend.
- Conversation recall (B): the `search_history` agent tool and its sanitizer.
- Absence-claim verification (C): the claim-verifier module, invoked in the multi-step pipeline.
- Entity canonicalization (D): the entity-registry module, the prompt-resolver anchoring hook, the retriever's query path, and the per-request context variable.
- Full-document re-grounding (E): the multi-step step-answerer and the retriever's full-text method.

The implementation requires no specialized hardware and runs fully offline against local models.

16. Prior-art declaration

This document and the techniques it describes were authored by Roberto Wenzel and are disclosed publicly as of **27 June 2026**. It is published to ensure these methods and their enumerated variants remain available to the public and to serve as prior art in any subsequent examination of patentability. The author asserts authorship of the specific contributions delineated and distinguished in §14 (Related work) and retains copyright in this text; consistent with §14, **no claim of priority is made over constituent primitives that already have established prior art**. It is released under CC BY 4.0 (see §0); anyone may reproduce, redistribute, and adapt it for any purpose, including prior-art search and patent examination, with attribution.

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Wenzel, R. (2026). *Deterministic, Model-Independent Grounding-Integrity Mechanisms for Retrieval-Augmented and Agentic Language-Model Systems*. Defensive publication, 27 June 2026. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20951506>

(Citation metadata is also provided in the project's `CITATION.cff` . DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20951506](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20951506), archived on Zenodo.)

17. References

- Akari Asai, Zeqiu Wu, Yizhong Wang, Avirup Sil, Hannaneh Hajishirzi. 2024. Self-RAG: Learning to Retrieve, Generate, and Critique through Self-Reflection. ICLR 2024 (Oral). arXiv:2310.11511. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.11511>
- Paolo Astrino. 2025. Local Hybrid Retrieval-Augmented Document QA. arXiv preprint. arXiv:2511.10297. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.10297>
- Bernd Bohnet, Vinh Q. Tran, Pat Verga, Roei Aharoni, Daniel Andor, Livio Baldini Soares, Massimiliano Ciaramita, Jacob Eisenstein, Kuzman Ganchev, Jonathan Herzig, Kai Hui, Tom Kwiatkowski, Ji Ma, Jianmo Ni, Lierni Sestorain Saralegui, Tal Schuster, William W. Cohen, Michael Collins, Dipanjan Das, Donald Metzler, Slav Petrov, Kellie Webster. 2022. Attributed Question Answering: Evaluation and Modeling for Attributed Large Language Models. arXiv preprint. arXiv:2212.08037. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.08037>
- Jiawei Chen, Hongyu Lin, Xianpei Han, Le Sun. 2024. Benchmarking Large Language Models in Retrieval-Augmented Generation. AACL 2024. arXiv:2309.01431. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.01431>
- Peter Christen. 2012. A Survey of Indexing Techniques for Scalable Record Linkage and Deduplication. IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering (TKDE), 24(9):1537-1555. doi:10.1109/TKDE.2011.127. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2011.127>
- Gordon V. Cormack, Charles L. A. Clarke, Stefan Büttcher. 2009. Reciprocal Rank Fusion outperforms Condorcet and individual Rank Learning Methods. SIGIR 2009, pp. 758-759. doi:10.1145/1571941.1572114. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1571941.1572114>
- Fred J. Damerau. 1964. A technique for computer detection and correction of spelling errors. Communications of the ACM, 7(3):171-176. doi:10.1145/363958.363994. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/363958.363994>
- Maxime Dassen, Rebecca Kotula, Kenton Murray, Andrew Yates, Dawn Lawrie, Efsun Kayi, James Mayfield, Kevin Duh. 2026. FACTUM: Mechanistic Detection of Citation Hallucination in Long-Form RAG. ECIR 2026 (Advances in Information Retrieval). arXiv:2601.05866. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2601.05866>
- Luyu Gao, Zhuyun Dai, Panupong Pasupat, Anthony Chen, Arun Tejasvi Chaganty, Yicheng Fan, Vincent Zhao, Ni Lao, Hongrae Lee, Da-Cheng Juan, Kelvin Guu. 2023. RARR: Researching and Revising What Language Models Say, Using Language Models. ACL 2023 (Volume 1: Long Papers), pp. 16477-16508. doi:10.18653/v1/2023.acl-long.910. <https://aclanthology.org/2023.acl-long.910/>
- Tianyu Gao, Howard Yen, Jiatong Yu, Danqi Chen. 2023. Enabling Large Language Models to Generate Text with Citations. EMNLP 2023, pp. 6465-6488. arXiv:2305.14627. doi:10.18653/v1/2023.emnlp-main.398. <https://aclanthology.org/2023.emnlp-main.398/>
- Yunfan Gao, Yun Xiong, Xinyu Gao, Kangxiang Jia, Jinliu Pan, Yuxi Bi, Yi Dai, Jiawei Sun, Meng Wang, Haofen Wang. 2023. Retrieval-Augmented Generation for Large Language Models: A Survey.

arXiv preprint. arXiv:2312.10997. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.10997>

Lei Huang, Weijiang Yu, Weitao Ma, Weihong Zhong, Zhangyin Feng, Haotian Wang, Qianglong Chen, Weihua Peng, Xiaocheng Feng, Bing Qin, Ting Liu. 2023. A Survey on Hallucination in Large Language Models: Principles, Taxonomy, Challenges, and Open Questions. arXiv preprint (ACM TOIS). arXiv:2311.05232. doi:10.1145/3703155. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.05232>

Ziwei Ji, Nayeon Lee, Rita Frieske, Tiezheng Yu, Dan Su, Yan Xu, Etsuko Ishii, Yejin Bang, Andrea Madotto, Pascale Fung. 2023. Survey of Hallucination in Natural Language Generation. ACM Computing Surveys, 55(12), Article 248. doi:10.1145/3571730. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3571730>

Vladimir Karpukhin, Barlas Oğuz, Sewon Min, Patrick Lewis, Ledell Wu, Sergey Edunov, Danqi Chen, Wen-tau Yih. 2020. Dense Passage Retrieval for Open-Domain Question Answering. EMNLP 2020, pp. 6769-6781. arXiv:2004.04906. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2004.04906>

V. I. Levenshtein. 1966. Binary codes capable of correcting deletions, insertions, and reversals. Soviet Physics Doklady, 10(8):707-710. <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1966SPhD...10..707L/abstract>

Patrick Lewis, Ethan Perez, Aleksandra Piktus, Fabio Petroni, Vladimir Karpukhin, Naman Goyal, Heinrich Küttler, Mike Lewis, Wen-tau Yih, Tim Rocktäschel, Sebastian Riedel, Douwe Kiela. 2020. Retrieval-Augmented Generation for Knowledge-Intensive NLP Tasks. NeurIPS 2020. arXiv:2005.11401. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.11401>

Dongfang Li, Zetian Sun, Xinshuo Hu, Zhenyu Liu, Ziyang Chen, Baotian Hu, Aiguo Wu, Min Zhang. 2023. A Survey of Large Language Models Attribution. arXiv preprint. arXiv:2311.03731. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.03731>

Junyi Li, Hwee Tou Ng. 2024. Think&Cite: Improving Attributed Text Generation with Self-Guided Tree Search and Progress Reward Modeling. arXiv preprint (later published at ACL 2025). arXiv:2412.14860. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.14860>

Weitao Li, Junkai Li, Weizhi Ma, Yang Liu. 2024. Citation-Enhanced Generation for LLM-based Chatbots. ACL 2024 (Volume 1: Long Papers), pp. 1451-1466. arXiv:2402.16063. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.acl-long.79/>

Nelson F. Liu, Tianyi Zhang, Percy Liang. 2023. Evaluating Verifiability in Generative Search Engines. Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2023. arXiv:2304.09848. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.09848>

Adyasha Maharana, Dong-Ho Lee, Sergey Tulyakov, Mohit Bansal, Francesco Barbieri, Yuwei Fang. 2024. Evaluating Very Long-Term Conversational Memory of LLM Agents. ACL 2024 (Volume 1: Long Papers), pp. 13851-13870. doi:10.18653/v1/2024.acl-long.747. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.acl-long.747/>

Potsawee Manakul, Adian Liusie, Mark J. F. Gales. 2023. SelfCheckGPT: Zero-Resource Black-Box Hallucination Detection for Generative Large Language Models. EMNLP 2023. arXiv:2303.08896. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.08896>

Sewon Min, Kalpesh Krishna, Xinxu Lyu, Mike Lewis, Wen-tau Yih, Pang Wei Koh, Mohit Iyyer, Luke Zettlemoyer, Hannaneh Hajishirzi. 2023. FActScore: Fine-grained Atomic Evaluation of Factual Precision in Long Form Text Generation. EMNLP 2023. arXiv:2305.14251. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.14251>

Rodrigo Nogueira, Kyunghyun Cho. 2019. Passage Re-ranking with BERT. arXiv preprint. arXiv:1901.04085. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1901.04085>

Volodymyr Ovcharov. 2026. Citation Grounding: Detecting and Reducing LLM Citation Hallucinations via Legal Citation Graphs. arXiv preprint. arXiv:2606.00898. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2606.00898>

Charles Packer, Sarah Wooders, Kevin Lin, Vivian Fang, Shishir G. Patil, Ion Stoica, Joseph E. Gonzalez. 2023. MemGPT: Towards LLMs as Operating Systems. arXiv preprint. arXiv:2310.08560. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.08560>

Joon Sung Park, Joseph C. O'Brien, Carrie J. Cai, Meredith Ringel Morris, Percy Liang, Michael S. Bernstein. 2023. Generative Agents: Interactive Simulacra of Human Behavior. UIST 2023. arXiv:2304.03442. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.03442>

Haosheng Qian, Yixing Fan, Jiafeng Guo, Ruqing Zhang, Qi Chen, Dawei Yin, Xueqi Cheng. 2025. VeriCite: Towards Reliable Citations in Retrieval-Augmented Generation via Rigorous Verification. SIGIR-AP 2025. arXiv:2510.11394. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.11394>

Pranav Rajpurkar, Robin Jia, Percy Liang. 2018. Know What You Don't Know: Unanswerable Questions for SQuAD. ACL 2018. arXiv:1806.03822. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1806.03822>

Nils Reimers, Iryna Gurevych. 2019. Sentence-BERT: Sentence Embeddings using Siamese BERT-Networks. EMNLP-IJCNLP 2019, pp. 3982-3992. doi:10.18653/v1/D19-1410. <https://aclanthology.org/D19-1410/>

Stephen E. Robertson, Hugo Zaragoza. 2009. The Probabilistic Relevance Framework: BM25 and Beyond. Foundations and Trends in Information Retrieval, 3(4):333-389. doi:10.1561/15000000019. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1561/15000000019>

Ozge Sevgili, Artem Shelmanov, Mikhail Arkhipov, Alexander Panchenko, Chris Biemann. 2022. Neural Entity Linking: A Survey of Models Based on Deep Learning. Semantic Web Journal, 13(3):527-570. arXiv:2006.00575. doi:10.3233/SW-222986. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.00575>

Wei Shen, Jianyong Wang, Jiawei Han. 2015. Entity Linking with a Knowledge Base: Issues, Techniques, and Solutions. IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering (TKDE), 27(2):443-460. doi:10.1109/TKDE.2014.2327028. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2014.2327028>

James Thorne, Andreas Vlachos, Christos Christodoulopoulos, Arpit Mittal. 2018. FEVER: a Large-scale Dataset for Fact Extraction and VERification. NAACL-HLT 2018 (Volume 1: Long Papers), pp. 809-819. arXiv:1803.05355. doi:10.18653/v1/N18-1074. <https://aclanthology.org/N18-1074/>

Amir Pouran Ben Veyseh, Franck Dernoncourt, Quan Hung Tran, Thien Huu Nguyen. 2020. What Does This Acronym Mean? Introducing a New Dataset for Acronym Identification and

Disambiguation. COLING 2020, pp. 3285-3301. doi:10.18653/v1/2020.coling-main.292.
<https://aclanthology.org/2020.coling-main.292/>

Jonas Wallat, Maria Heuss, Maarten de Rijke, Avishek Anand. 2024. Correctness is not Faithfulness in RAG Attributions. arXiv preprint. arXiv:2412.18004. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.18004>

Orion Weller, Marc Marone, Nathaniel Weir, Dawn Lawrie, Daniel Khashabi, Benjamin Van Durme. 2023. "According to ...": Prompting Language Models Improves Quoting from Pre-Training Data. arXiv preprint; accepted to EACL 2024. arXiv:2305.13252. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.13252>

Shunyu Yao, Jeffrey Zhao, Dian Yu, Nan Du, Izhak Shafran, Karthik Narasimhan, Yuan Cao. 2023. ReAct: Synergizing Reasoning and Acting in Language Models. ICLR 2023. arXiv:2210.03629. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.03629>

Zhangyue Yin, Qiushi Sun, Qipeng Guo, Jiawen Wu, Xipeng Qiu, Xuanjing Huang. 2023. Do Large Language Models Know What They Don't Know? Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: ACL 2023. arXiv:2305.18153. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.18153>

Xinyan Velocity Yu, Sewon Min, Luke Zettlemoyer, Hannaneh Hajishirzi. 2023. CREPE: Open-Domain Question Answering with False Presuppositions. ACL 2023 (Volume 1: Long Papers). arXiv:2211.17257. doi:10.18653/v1/2023.acl-long.583. <https://aclanthology.org/2023.acl-long.583/>

Hongbang Yuan, Pengfei Cao, Zhuoran Jin, Yubo Chen, Daojian Zeng, Kang Liu, Jun Zhao. 2024. Whispers that Shake Foundations: Analyzing and Mitigating False Premise Hallucinations in Large Language Models. arXiv preprint. arXiv:2402.19103. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.19103>

Wanjun Zhong, Lianghong Guo, Qiqi Gao, He Ye, Yanlin Wang. 2024. MemoryBank: Enhancing Large Language Models with Long-Term Memory. AAAI 2024, 38(17):19724-19731. arXiv:2305.10250. doi:10.1609/aaai.v38i17.29946. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.10250>

Software and documentation (non-archival sources)

- Onyx (open-source project). Citation processor — `backend/onyx/chat/citation_processor.py`. <https://github.com/onyx-dot-app/onyx> (accessed 22 June 2026).
- Anthropic. Citations. Claude Developer Platform documentation. <https://platform.claude.com/docs/en/docs/build-with-claude/citations> (accessed 22 June 2026).